

Requirement Elicitation Interview Experiment

In our research which entitled as "Utilizing New Technologies in Requirement Elicitation Interviews to Improve the Learning Outcome of the Students", we aim to measure the usability and usefulness of new technologies in requirement elicitation interviews. The experiment is created by Binnur Gorer as a research line of her Ph.D. studies at Bogazici University under the supervision of Asst. Prof. Fatma Basak Aydemir.

In this experiment, we create a requirements elicitation interview scenario where you will play the role of the analyst and our system will play the role of the client. The interview will be conducted via Zoom. Before joining the experiment, please ensure your camera and microphone are working properly. We may request you to keep your video and microphone ON during the experiment. You are expected to follow the requests and guidelines provided by the system and complete the interview and the training. You can leave the experiment at any time and for any reason.

If you have any questions relating to the processing and the purposes of collecting the data in question, do not hesitate to contact us at the following email: binnur.gorer@boun.edu.tr

Thank you in advance for your collaboration!

* Indicates required question

Welcome to our experiment ! Below is the video introduct...

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=7Ezdn-iG-ic>

Please fill your information and provide your consent

1. First Name *

2. Last Name *

3. Email Address *

4. Consent request *

Check all that apply.

I hereby consent to participate in the experiment and allow my video tapes to be taken for academic purposes.

Demographics

Please answer the following questions in order to help us to learn more about you

5. Age *

6. Gender *

Mark only one oval.

Female

Male

Rather not say

7. Current occupation (Select all that apply) *

Check all that apply.

- Undergraduate student
- Graduate student
- Analyst
- Software Developer
- Software Tester
- Other: _____

8. How many years of professional experience working in the industry you have? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0
- 1-3
- 4-6
- more than 6 years

9. How many mock requirement elicitation interviews you had up to now? (conducted with simulated customers, including the ones for class projects etc.) *

Mark only one oval.

- 0
- 1-3
- 4-6
- more than 6

10. How many real requirement elicitation interviews you had up to now? (conducted with real customers) *

Mark only one oval.

- 0
- 1-3
- 4-6
- more than 6

11. Which kind of training you have in order to learn how to conduct requirement elicitation interviews? (Select all that apply) *

Check all that apply.

- I do not have any training on this
- Self study
- University course
- Company trainings
- Other: _____

12. I have very good theoretical understanding of requirement elicitation interview techniques.

*

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

13. I feel confident and comfortable in practicing requirement elicitation interviews *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

Perception of Robots and New Technologies

We would like to get some idea about how you perceive robots and new technologies. Please answer the questions below.

14. I would feel uneasy if robots really had emotions. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

15. Something bad might happen if robots developed into living beings. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

16. I would feel relaxed talking with robots. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

17. I would feel uneasy if I had to do my work with help of a robot. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

18. If robots had emotions I would be able to make friends with them *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

19. I feel good being with robots that have emotions *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

20. The word "robot" means nothing to me *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

21. I would feel nervous using a robot in front of other people *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

22. I would hate the idea that robots or intelligent computers were making judgments about things *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

23. I would feel very nervous just standing in front of a robot *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

24. I feel that if I depend on robots too much, something bad might happen. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

25. I would feel paranoid talking with a robot. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

26. I am concerned that robots would be a bad influence on younger children. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

27. I feel that in the future society will be dominated by robots. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

Interview Perception and Management

28. I feel that my verbal communication skills are strong. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

29. While taking an interview, I become concerned that the interviewer will perceive me as socially awkward. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

30. I am overwhelmed by thoughts of doing poorly when I am in interview situations *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

31. Before an interview I am so nervous that I spend an excessive amount of time on my appearance *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

32. During the interviews, I often can not think of a thing to say. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

33. During an interview, I worry about what will happen if the interview is not satisfied with my performance. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

34. I get afraid about what kind of personal impression I am making on interviews. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

35. I often feel uneasy about my appearance when I am being interviewed. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

36. I become very uptight about having to socially interact with an interviewer. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

37. I worry about whether the interviewer will like me as a person *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

38. In interviews, I get nervous about whether my performance is good enough. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

39. I get anxious in the interviews that I am unable to express my thoughts clearly. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

40. During an interview, I worry that my actions will not be considered socially appropriate.

*

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

41. During an interview, I am so troubled by thoughts of failing that my performance is reduced. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

42. During the interviews, I find it hard to understand what the interviewer is asking me. *

Mark only one oval.

strongly disagree

1

2

3

4

5

strongly agree

Skip to section 5 (Ready for Experiment !)

Ready for Experiment !

Thank you for your answers. Now you can start the experiment by using the meeting information below. Do not forget to save the information before clicking the submit button.

Requirement Elicitation Interview Agent is inviting you to a scheduled Zoom meeting.

Topic: Requirements Elicitation Interview Experiment

Join Zoom Meeting

<https://boun-edu-tr.zoom.us/j/5263071266?pwd=TFQvNDY5TVF5aFc0QUQvQWZXMnpEZz09>

Meeting ID: 526 307 1266

Passcode: 1234

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